

Validating the Weiskopf 3x3 Data Quality Assessment Framework

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BACKGROUND AND RATIONALE

Electronic health record (EHR) data offers both providers and researchers a unique opportunity to improve health-related decision-making and patient-related outcomes. The Health Information Technology for Economic and Clinical Health (HITECH) Act of 2009 created Medicare and Medicaid incentive programs (CMS) that increased meaningful use and adoption of EHRs.^{1,2} As of March 2015, more than \$29.6 billion in CMS incentive program payments had been made and more than 400,000 eligible professionals, hospitals, and critical access hospitals received payment for participating in a CMS incentive program.³ This resulting large-scale deployment of EHRs has not only increased the speed at which hospitals and providers can access patient information, but has also increased the amount of data available for secondary use.⁴

EHR data is often used to solve complicated clinical problems.⁵⁻⁷ While an incredibly informative data source, it is notoriously known to violate several fundamental assumptions of data quality (DQ).⁸ Incompleteness of records, inconsistency of records across time, and unexplained missingness are common DQ issues affecting the usability of this data source.⁹ The use of EHR data for research purposes has also grown; and many important health-related questions have and will continue to be answered through the analysis of this data source.¹⁰ While efforts are currently being made to define and establish methods to reliably validate these types of data,¹¹ accurate, standardized methodologies have yet to be identified. In a review of 35 empirical studies, Chan et al¹² found a substantial lack of agreement regarding which DQ dimensions were assessed. Specifically, they found that of the included studies 23% assessed data comparability, 57% completeness, and 66% accuracy. A more recent review of DQ

assessment methods by Weiskopf and Weng found that of the 95 articles examined, there were over 20 unique features used to assess DQ.⁹

Recently, Weiskopf developed a 3x3 DQ assessment framework (Figure 1), which includes the assessment of three DQ dimensions across three data dimensions (i.e., patient, variables, and time).¹³ The DQ dimensions included in the framework are: complete (i.e., data are sufficient in quantity for given task); correct (i.e., data are without error); and current (i.e., data recorded at a desired relative or absolute time(s)).^{13(p133)} As illustrated in Figure 1, each of the cells within the framework contains a question representing a proposed operationalization of its specific data x DQ dimension.

Figure 1. Weiskopf 3x3 DQ Assessment Framework¹³

	A: Complete	B: Correct	C: Current
1: Patient	1A Are there sufficient data points for each patient?	1B Is the distribution of values across patients plausible?	1C Were all data recorded during the timeframe of interest?
2: Variables	2A Are there sufficient data points for each variable?	2B Is there concordance between variables?	2C Were variables recorded in the desired order?
3: Time	3A Are there sufficient data points for each time?	3B Is the progression of data over time plausible?	3C Were data recoded with the desired regularity over time?

Given the key features of a specific use case, a different subset or collection of the nine framework cells can be used. In theory, there are 512 distinct subsets that can be generated, but Weiskopf claims that only 26 of these are realistic.¹³⁽¹³⁶⁾ In addition to these subsets, Weiskopf also provides recommendations for how one could apply these operationalizations within a specific data set (i.e., measures, reports, examples, and references).¹³ Although this framework and its approach are well defined, utilizing multiple DQ x

data dimension combinations is both complicated and time consuming. Further, while the various combinations are very specific, they lack clearly defined, actionable measures.

Project Objectives

The current project aimed to provide quantitative measures for the Weiskopf's 3x3 DQ assessment framework. Specifically, the current project utilized a three-step process to validate the Weiskopf DQ assessment framework:

1. Develop data model-independent operational measures (i.e., descriptive statistics and visualizations) for each cell of the framework.
2. Implement the measures against the Observational Medical Outcomes Partnership (OMOP) common data model (CDM).^{14,15}
3. Field-test the operational measures using 2010-2014 Pediatric EHR Data Sharing Network (PEDSnet) OMOP-compliant data from Children's Hospital Colorado (CHCO).¹⁶

METHODS

The current project utilized data collected between 2010 and 2014; all available encounters and patients seen at CHCO during this time period were utilized. No direct identifiers were included in any of the data tables, thus patient confidentiality was protected. The current project was approved by the Colorado Multiple Institutional Review Board (COMIRB #15-0127) and supported through Dr. Michael Kahn's PCORI Contract (ME-1303-5581).

Data Source

All of the data used in the current project conformed to the structure defined by the PEDSnet OMOP CDM, which is an adaptation of the OMOP CDM version 4.0.¹⁴⁻¹⁶ This CDM was designed for secondary research, able to incorporate diverse data through integrating several vocabularies commonly used in the healthcare field (Table 1). Specific tables from this database used in the current study included: person (i.e., gender, date of birth, race, ethnicity, location); visit occurrence (i.e., patient dates and reasons for visit); procedure occurrence (i.e., processes ordered or carried out by a healthcare provider); and

condition occurrence (i.e., patient conditions or diagnoses). Data was extracted from the CHCO PEDSnet OMOP database using Oracle SQL Developer version 4.0.3.¹⁷

Table 1. Description of CHCO PEDSnet OMOP Database Tables Utilized in Final Data Set

Table	Description	N	Variables	Vocabularies
Person	Patient-level information including gender, year of birth, month of birth, and day of birth, race, ethnicity, location, provider, and care site.	560,451 ^a	16	HL7 ^b ; OMB ^b ; CDC ^b
Procedure Occurrence	Record or observation-level information on patient procedures to include procedure, procedure date, procedure type, associated provider, condition, and procedure.	769,648 ^a	9	CPT-4 ^b ; HCPCS ^b ; ICD-9 ^b ; ICD-9-CM ^b ; LOINC ^b ; OMOP; SNOMED ^b
Visit Occurrence	Record or observation-level information about patient visits to include visit start and end date, place of service, and care site.	3,350,801 ^a	7	OMOP; CMS ^b
Condition Occurrence	Record or observation-level information about patient diagnoses to include condition, condition start and end date, condition type, stop reason, and associated provider.	11,617,870 ^a	10	SNOMED; OMOP

^aFinal sample size is based off of data collected 2010-2014.

^bHealth Level Seven International (HL7); Office of Management and Budget (OMB); Centers for Disease Control (CDC); Current Procedure Terminology (CPT-4); Healthcare Common Procedure Coding System (HCPCS); International Classification of Diseases (ICD-9); International Classification of Diseases Clinical Modification (ICD-9-CM); Logical Observation Identifiers Names and Codes (LOINC); Systematized Nomenclature of Medicine—Clinical Terms (SNOWMED); Centers for Medicare & Medicaid Services (CMS).

Statistical Analyses

All analyses were performed using R version 3.1.2.¹⁸ The majority of statistical analyses were descriptive, utilizing frequency tables, means, medians, and standard deviations to develop the operational measures. Tests to compare counts between dependent groups were utilized in the process of field-testing the operational measures where appropriate. Since most patients were seen at least once a year, a McNemar chi-square test for dependent groups was utilized. Given the large amount of data in the final data set, inferential statistical analyses were sufficiently powered, but not necessarily clinically or operationally

meaningful.¹⁹ Thus, findings from inferential statistics were interpreted with caution and effect sizes for each analysis were provided.

RESULTS

The final data set utilized for measure development included data from 560,451 patients across 769,648 procedures, 3,350,801 visits, and 11,617,870 conditions (Table 1). Data model-independent operational measures (i.e., descriptive statistics and visualizations) for eight of the nine cells in the Weiskopf DQ assessment framework were developed (Figures 2-9); these measures were successfully implemented against the PEDSnet OMOP CDM. All of the measures are described with their field-testing results below. Because of the large sample sizes utilized, some of the developed measures required y-axis log-transformation in order to be visualized in a meaningful way. When this was required, the actual counts were provided and the y-axis removed to ensure accurate and clear representation of the data.

Complete: Patient

This cell of the 3x3 framework examined whether a variable of interest had sufficient patient-level data.¹³ Of the 560,451 available patients, 130,827 (23.33%) had at least one complete procedure between 2010-2014. To operationalize this cell, a complete visit percentage was calculated for each patient. To do this,

the count of complete associated provider id data (numerator) was divided by the count of complete procedure occurrence id data (denominator) for each patient. The patient-specific percent of complete procedures across all patients were then

plotted in a histogram using 10% bin widths. Results from field-testing this measure (Figure 2), revealed that over 99% of all patients run during this time had complete visit information (i.e., a documented

procedure associated with a provider). In comparison, only 26 (0.02%) patients had a documented procedure without an associated provider. Further examination of these patients' records is recommended.

Complete: Variables

This cell of the 3x3 framework examined whether a variable of interest had sufficient data points.¹³ Of the 769,648 procedures, 769,399 (99.97%) of observations had complete associated provider id data that could be utilized for measure development. To operationalize this cell, counts of complete and missing

observations for the associated provider id variable were calculated and summarized. Field-testing this measure (Figure 3) revealed that most procedures conducted between 2010-2014 had complete associated provider id data.

While only a small portion of the observations for this variable were missing, additional follow-up regarding the 249 missing observations may be warranted.

Complete: Time

This cell of the 3x3 framework examined the sufficiency of data points for each time point or interval of

interest.¹³ To operationalize this cell, separate counts of complete and missing associated provider id observations were aggregated by year (2010-2014). Field-testing this measure (Figure 4) revealed that the majority of

associated provider id observations over time were complete (>99.91%, range: 111,759-196,445). In comparison, the counts of missing associated provider id observations varied from 7 (2010) to 180 (2014).

Correct: Patient

This cell of the 3x3 framework examined the whether the distribution of values across a variable of interest was plausible for the current population.¹³ To operationalize this cell, counts of patients seen

between 2010-2014 were aggregated by year of birth. Field-testing this measure (Figure 5) indicated patients were born between 1909 and 2014 ($M=2003.36$, $SD=8.20$). Deeper investigation revealed 510 (0.10%)

patients with a year of birth prior to 1940. Patients in the CHCO database should not have been born prior to 1940, thus this finding represents a DQ anomaly. Further examination of these records is needed.

Correct: Variables

This cell of the 3x3 framework examined whether or not there was agreement between variables of

interest.¹³ Of the 3,350,801 visit occurrence observations, 1,423,263 (42.48%) observations had complete start and end timestamp information that could be utilized for measure development. To operationalize this cell, the visit occurrence start and end timestamp variables were

compared and categorized according to whether the start and end timestamps occurred at the same time,

whether the start timestamp occurred before the end timestamp or whether the start timestamp occurred after the end timestamp. Once complete, counts for each visit occurrence temporal ordering category were stratified by place of service. Field-testing this measure (Figure 6) revealed the Ambulatory Surgery (N=31, 0.02%), Inpatient (N=10, 0.03%), and outpatient (N=557, 0.02%) place of service locations had observations with erroneous visit occurrence temporal ordering. This is a DQ anomaly, further examination of these observations is strongly recommended.

Correct: Time

This cell of the 3x3 framework examined whether the progression of data for a given variable of interest was plausible over time.¹³ To operationalize this cell, Emergency Department (ER) visit occurrence counts were aggregated by year (2010-2014) and then stratified by month. Field-testing this measure (Figure 7) revealed similar monthly trends in years 2012-2014. ER visits during the month of December for years 2010 and 2011 appeared to differ from 2012-2014 (2010:N=6,131, 2011:N=5,553,

2012:N=8,142, 2013:N=6,760, 2014:N=8,524). To provide an illustration of whether these differences were statistically meaningful, the counts of December ER visits in 2010 and 2011 were compared to the counts of December ER visits in 2012-2014 using

McNemars chi-square tests. Results revealed that the counts of December ER visits in 2010 were significantly lower than the counts of December ER visits in 2012-2014 ($\chi^2(1, N=35,110)=588.20, p<.001, OR=0.106, 95\% CI[0.102, 0.109]$). Further, the counts of December ER visits in 2011 were significantly lower than the counts of December ER visits in 2012-2014 ($\chi^2(1, N=35,110)=709.23, p<.001, OR=0.094, 95\% CI[0.090, 0.097]$). While both of these results have highly significant p-values

(which is not surprising given the large sample size), the corresponding odds ratios (i.e., measure of effect size) were also large in magnitude (i.e., far away from a value of 1.0). While lower counts of December ER visits in 2010 and 2011 are consistent with lower rates of community influenza rates recorded by the Colorado Department of Public Health and Environment (the major driver of pediatric ER visits in December), further investigation is recommended.²⁰⁻²¹

Current: Patient

This cell of the 3x3 framework examined whether all of the data was entered for a specific timeframe of interest.¹³ Of the 560,451 patients, 512,598 (91.46%) had complete visit occurrence data that could be utilized for measure development. To operationalize this cell, a new variable was created which stored the

total time in six-month intervals, from today’s date (April 1, 2015 was used when field-testing this measure), since each patient was last seen. Fielding-testing this measure (Figure 8) revealed cumulative frequencies showing that 32.91% of patients had been seen within the last year,

54.74% within the last two years, 71.09% within the last three years, 83.38% within the last four years, 94.31% within the last five years, and 100% within the last six years.

Current: Variables

This cell of the 3x3 framework examined whether variables of interest were recorded in a desired order.¹³ Unfortunately, a measure for this cell of the framework could not be operationalized without invoking specific meaningful use criteria (e.g., tracking the ordering of events related to a specific clinical condition) or without access to metadata (i.e., information regarding how frequently data is extracted from the EPIC CLARITY database and loaded into the PEDSnet OMOP CDM). While utilizing

meaningful use criteria would have been possible, doing so would have resulted in a measure that could not be generalized beyond that particular example. Accessing metadata was not included in the approved version of the COMIRB protocol and thus was not within the scope of the current project.

Current: Time

This cell of the 3x3 framework examined whether data were entered for a variable of interest at a desired regularity over time.¹³ To operationalize this cell, the average days between each patients' first and last

visit occurrence for each year (2010-2014) was calculated. Field-testing this measure (Figure 9) revealed similarities in the average number of days between patient visits each year. On average, there were 71.47 days ($SD=104.06$) between visits in 2010, 68.57

days ($SD=102.42$) in 2011, 70.48 days ($SD=103.72$) in 2012, 71.87 days ($SD=104.34$) in 2013, and 72.08 days ($SD=104.20$) in 2014.

CONCLUSIONS AND PUBLIC HEALTH SIGNIFICANCE

If the pursuit of personalized medicine is dependent upon the integration of large amounts of diverse patient-specific data, then the precision of personalized medicine will ultimately be dependent upon the quality of each patient's data. Given the popularity of secondary use of EHR data to answer complicated public health questions, an understanding of the usability of this data source is of paramount importance. Although many dimensions of DQ exist in the literature, the Weiskopf 3x3 DQ assessment framework may be one of the most comprehensive to date. Research has already identified qualitative operationalizations for each of the cells within the framework, but quantitative validation had not been performed prior to the current study. The current study was able to develop operational descriptive

measures and visualizations for eight of the nine cells of the framework. Furthermore, these measures and visualizations were created in a manner allowing utilization on PEDSnet OMOP CDM-compliant as well as other CDM-independent EHR data sources. When field-testing these measures using CHCO data collected between 2010-2014, several interesting DQ anomalies were detected.

Limitations

While quantitatively validating the Weiskopf 3x3 DQ assessment framework utilizing pediatric data is an important contribution, analysis-driven validation efforts utilizing alternative data sources are crucial for ensuring generalizability of the measures. Additionally, only a small subset of the CHCO PEDSnet OMOP CDM database was utilized in the current project. Applying the operational measures and visualizations to the full database may be informative for refining the measures. The final data set that was used had been highly processed in the process of being extracted from the native EHR format (EPIC Clarity) into the PEDSnet OMOP CDM format, thus the quantity of DQ findings in our results is significantly lower than rates observed by others using primary (or raw) EHR data.

NEXT STEPS

Future work should aim to determining whether an operational measure for the final cell of the DQ assessment framework (Current x Variable) is possible or if modifying this cell's definition is more appropriate. Additionally, future work should examine whether the current R code developed for this project could be used to create an R package or if it could be incorporated into existing open source data-quality tools or applications (i.e., Observational Health Data Sciences and Informatics Achilles Web tool).²²

ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

I would like to thank Dr. Michael Kahn, Dr. Nicole Weiskopf, and Dr. Sarah Schmiede for their support and guidance throughout the Capstone project. Additionally, I would like to thank the staff from the Clinical Research Informatics Core and the IT Department at CHCO for supporting my project and for helping me gain access to the database. Finally, I would like to thank Professor Edward Dauer, LL.B MPH and my fellow Capstone classmates for their invaluable feedback, support, and advice.

CAPSTONE PROJECT REFLECTION

I feel that completing a Capstone project is an important experience for students who want to pursue careers in the field of public health. The Capstone course is designed to teach students about the importance of conducting different types of projects relevant to the diverse specializations within the field. While my project was applicable to Biostatistics, because of the collaborative design of the course, I was also exposed to projects in the Epidemiology, Community and Behavioral Health, Occupational and Environmental Health, and Health Systems Management and Policy specializations. This course also provided me with the opportunity to work with students I had never met before. Additionally, through the different Capstone course activities and presentations, I got to learn about different quantitative analysis techniques (i.e., cost-effectiveness analysis) that I had not been exposed to in my Biostatistics courses.

Achievements

Utilizing R to create a database connection to a relational database stored on a virtual machine was not something that I knew how to do on my own prior to this project. Having completed this project I now have the skills necessary to do this. Additionally, my final capstone data set had over 11 million rows. To confidentially work a data set this large required improvements in both my analytical and computational skills. Finally, during the Capstone course we are required to practice presenting our project to the class twice. I have never been confident speaking in front of others, having to present multiple times prior to the Public Health Symposium helped improve my confidence.

Challenges

The biggest challenge experienced during my Capstone was getting COMIRB approval. It took roughly two months to get my protocol approved, which meant that I was not able to start working with the data until mid-February. When I was finally able to gain access, it took an additional week to get the necessary access privileges installed on my virtual machine. I was only able to successfully access the data for a few weeks; my VM crashed and was unable to be repaired for several weeks. Not being able to access the data made it challenging to edit my measures and visualizations. Luckily, my access was restored by the beginning of April and I was able to finalize my measures and visualization.

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